

Evaluation Report for

TEBT-2023-0008

Submission Title	Is it useful to have a translational review or translational review method in toxicology and occupational health for policy-decision makers?
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Status	In Editorial Review ▾
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Evaluation Round	Editorial review round 2
Recommendation	Revise ▾
Handling Editor's Summary	This revised manuscript describes a “translational review” approach to timely summarisation of evidence for policy-makers. The editor’s opinion is that the revisions made do not yet sufficiently articulate or address the complex issues associated with providing scientific support to decision-makers. This risks presenting an over-simplified account of a complex problem and its potential solutions that could mislead the intended users of “translational review”. This is partly due to the submitted format of the manuscript, as brief correspondence, not being appropriate to its objectives or scope. The editors therefore continue to recommend extensive revisions be made before the manuscript can be considered for publication in our journal.

Basic information checklist

Passed?	Item checked
Y ▾	Preprint, relevant revision materials, and supplemental material available on Zenodo
Y ▾	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDs (if available) of each author are present

N/A ▾	Structured abstract has been provided
Y ▾	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement have been given
Y ▾	Complete funding details are given, or “no funding” is declared
Y ▾	An informative disclosure of interests for all authors has been provided, or disclosure refused
Y ▾	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited, if relevant (TOP 1, level 3)
Y ▾	Data and code availability has been stated and links to both are functional
Y ▾	One or more appropriate reporting checklists for submission type have been completed
Y ▾	Supplemental materials have plain English file names

Editorial Evaluation, Round 02

Level of satisfaction with the revisions the authors have made to the manuscript?
Very unsatisfied ▾ to Somewhat unsatisfied ▾
Reasons for the level of satisfaction
<p>Reviewer 1: I suggested extensive revisions to the manuscript. This was on the basis that a paper purporting to present a new type of evidence synthesis methodology, recommended to be used in scientific advisory contexts, ought to be rigorously articulated. The authors have made few of the revisions that I suggested, while not providing a convincing counterargument that such a brief overview of the proposed methodology is appropriate given the goals of the submission.</p> <p>Reviewer 2: The authors have implemented some of the revisions suggested such as that to provide an illustrative example. However, this example reveals some of the limitations of the proposed method and these appear not to have been identified or adequately reflected upon by the authors. Specifically, the solution proposed to address difficulties associated with devising generic search terms for chemical exposures is likely to miss much of the relevant recent literature and the potentially large number of systematic reviews retrieved if an adequate search strategy had been applied is not recognised. The current version of the revised manuscript fails to answer the question posed in its title.</p>
Further comments or suggestions for changes to the manuscript
<p>Reviewer 1 Since I believe most of my original comments still stand, I will add only a few additional observations.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The illustrative example is not detailed enough, lacking details on the topic, context, and success of the use of the methodology. Too much opinion is still presented as uncited fact. 2. The jargon issue has not really been resolved - for example, the authors still refer to their approach using two terms - even in the title: “a translational review or translational review method”.

3. The authors dismiss the suggestion that the proposed method be put in context with other potentially similar methodological developments, as being a “modest expert opinion”. I still believe it to be no such thing - the authors cannot recommend an approach without a much fuller articulation of what that approach is and why, in their opinion, it is useful. It is not enough for the authors to just assert their expert opinion as to its utility.

4. The author instructions relating to correspondence are not relevant to an article that in my opinion ought not be published as correspondence. Likewise, the suggestion to write about 800 words was guidance given before the manuscript was seen by the editor and should not be interpreted as binding.

5. There are still puzzles in what the authors intend by their processes. This includes assessing bias in a SR but not the suitability of the SR for informing the context of the decision - but then using tools like AMSTAR and CREST that do not assess bias, while omitting mention of ROBIS - the one tool purposefully developed for risk of bias assessment of SRs (Whiting et al., 2016). This contributes to the feeling that there is a mismatch between the rigour of articulation of the approach and the authors' goals in developing this manuscript.

6. The approach seems to boil down to something as simple as: search for a relevant SR, pick the most recent or relevant, summarise its findings for the policy-maker. If that is the case, it seems like quite a limited method about which many questions could be asked. Giving it a rather grandiose name like “translational review methodology” feels rather unearned.

7. Listing limitations is insufficient - their potential impact and how they are to be managed also needs to be articulated, or the mentioning of the limitation is not useful.

8. Fundamentally, I don't think the authors can have it both ways - it can't be an approach significant enough that it warrants a new entry in the typology of reviews, yet so minor that it does not warrant a full accounting of what the approach is. If I were a decision-maker looking to be persuaded of the merits of this approach, I would need a lot more information than I am being provided with here.

9. It occurs to me that it may be helpful for revising this manuscript to view it as an exercise in convincing a policy-maker that translational review would be a valuable addition to their advisory toolbox.

10. Rigour is a key criterion for publication in our journal. It may well be that we are just not the right venue for a manuscript of this exact form. If the authors feel this is the case, they would be perfectly within their rights to withdraw their manuscript for submission elsewhere.

11. I would recommend against reviewing this manuscript again, unless substantial changes along the above lines have been made.

Reviewer 2

Based on personal experience of having to conduct reviews of the literature aimed at decision makers within a timeframe that would not allow a systematic review, including attempts to conduct standardised umbrella reviews, I would invite the authors to reflect further on the following points.

1. Devising search strategies that can adequately identify the relevant reviews for chemical exposures is fiendishly difficult as title and abstract or even full text may not mention the terms ‘chemical’ or ‘substance’ but instead refer to a specific substance by one of its many names, its specific use(s) (e.g. cleaning agents), or a hazardous property (e.g. irritant or carcinogen). A generic search term is therefore likely to

miss much of the relevant literature. It is also unclear whether relevant global statistics about deaths and DALYs related to unintentional poisoning would have been picked up. The authors should discuss this issue that is specific to chemical exposures and the feasibility of devising an adequate search strategy in a few hours.

2. From the little detail given about this illustrative example, it seems that the literature retrieved could have been identified through other search strategies such as targeted manual searches of the grey literature and relevant databases. The authors should reflect further on whether other strategies could lead to similar or more exhaustive results more effectively.

3. A further issue that has not been mentioned and is specific to the problematic of occupational exposures is that while monitoring data of such occupational exposures must exist, it seems to not be made publicly available or difficult to access. Reflections on difficulties to access all existing evidence would be a valuable addition to this manuscript.

4. A more comprehensive search strategy may have yielded many more systematic reviews and meta-analyses. In some cases, there may be as many such secondary studies as primary studies, which results in little time gain in adopting a review of review methods and may require additional steps to select the most relevant, recent and/or robust secondary study, further compounded by the diversity of the types of chemical agents that may have been considered. How do the authors propose to address these issues?

5. In their example, the authors mention studies that report estimates of the burden of disease (mortality, DALYs) rather than summary risk ratios. The former may indeed be more intuitive and easier to communicate to decision makers than the latter. A discussion of this aspect and its implication for the search strategy would also be a welcome addition.

6. There are some minor issues with the text. The sentence “Due to societal pressures, the time to provide answers is increasing in proportion to the number of solicitations and requests for toxicological risk quantification, whereas the number of available subject matter experts is decreasing.” (L51-54) needs to be rephrased if the authors indeed meant to highlight that the fact that time to respond to such solicitations is decreasing rather than increasing. The ‘translational approach of reviews’ may instead mean ‘translational approach to reviews’.

References

Whiting, P. et al. (2016) ‘ROBIS: A new tool to assess risk of bias in systematic reviews was developed’, *Journal of clinical epidemiology*, 69(PG - 225-234), pp. 225–234. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2015.06.005>.